

Technology Transfer and Adaptability in Smart Irrigation Systems: A Classification Based on Country-Specific Performance Indicators

Turgut GÖKÇEK^a

a: PhD. C., İstanbul Ticaret University, 0000-0001-7816-9891, turgutgokcek@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationships of smart agricultural irrigation systems under different conditions. The research statistically analyzes the adaptability and effectiveness of these systems according to country development level, climate type, technological approach, crop type, and implementing institution. A total of 64 independent studies were included. Using the meta-analysis research method, a detailed literature review was conducted. The correlation coefficients obtained were converted into the widely used Fisher's Z values to allow for statistical comparisons and to prevent distortions in statistical results. Additionally, subgroup analyses were conducted to identify and reveal contextual differences. The findings indicate a high overall mean correlation ($r = 0.853$), demonstrating that these technologies have a strong impact on agricultural productivity. However, the high heterogeneity observed across all subgroups ($I^2 > 75\%$) shows that success depends not only on technical performance but also on environmental, social, and institutional factors. Examination of developed countries, temperate climates, AI/ML-based systems, and academic implementations reveals that the highest adaptability was found in these categories. In contrast, developing countries, tropical climates, and farmer-led applications faced challenges due to infrastructure limitations, data accuracy issues, and operational constraints. The results highlight the importance of technology transfer strategies necessary to enhance the success of digital transformation in agriculture.

Keywords: *Smart irrigation, meta-analysis, adaptability, digital agriculture, technology transfer, Fisher's Z transformation, agri-tech.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector has come to the fore as a strategic sector in the 21st century. The increasing global demand for food and the need to ensure the sustainability of the food supply chain reinforce this strategic position. With climate change, it is clear that food supply will need to be provided much more efficiently in the coming years. The rapidly growing global population, the environmental impacts of climate change, the depletion of water resources, food security issues, and the shrinking of agricultural lands are emerging as serious problems. According to data from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the world population is expected to reach 10 billion by 2050. Agricultural production must be increased by at least 60%. Increasing agricultural production to this extent is quite difficult using traditional methods. Meeting this food demand with limited resources seems unlikely. Therefore, there is a need for new technologies and the development of new production models (Bwambale, Abagale, and Anornu 2023; Masseroni, Arbat, and de Lima 2020).

With Industry 4.0, many smart agriculture technologies have entered our lives in agricultural production. Technologies that include digital solutions are particularly prominent. The Internet of Things (IoT) technology, which is one of the digital technologies, is becoming increasingly important as it represents a system that brings together many other smart technologies. The fact that it works in an integrated manner with many technologies such as big data analysis, artificial intelligence, smart sensors, and algorithms increases its importance in terms of representing an intelligent system as a whole (Ara et al. 2024). The Internet of Things (IoT) technology performs critical tasks in agricultural production and logistics very quickly and accurately. IoT technology enables data collection, analysis, and automatic decision-making processes in agricultural activities through this integrated work. It can monitor parameters such as soil moisture, air temperature, plant growth, pest detection, water level, and need status in real time through sensors. Thus, it can perform a critical task in decision-making processes quickly and accurately. In this context, IoT technology, which helps increase agricultural

production efficiency, has a significant impact on the automation of irrigation systems (Kaushik and Singh 2025).

The optimal use of water, one of the most consumed resources in agriculture, is at the forefront of today's environmental issues (Muharomah et al. 2025). IoT-based irrigation systems and other smart irrigation systems are making serious contributions to solving this problem. They help reduce production costs and prevent water wastage.

IoT-based irrigation and other smart irrigation systems, which are among the smart irrigation systems, ensure that the required amount of water reaches agricultural crops at the required time. However, the success of these smart irrigation systems depends on farmers' adaptation to and adoption of this technology. The success of these smart irrigation systems is not limited to technical adequacy.

It depends on numerous factors such as the effective use of technology in the field, farmer training, infrastructure, the establishment of financial support mechanisms, and local government policies. Therefore, progress must be made in areas such as farmer training, the effective use of technology in the field, and the provision of financial support.

At this point, another important concept is technology transfer. Although the concept of technology transfer is defined as the transfer of technology between countries, it does not only refer to physical transfer but also to the transfer of an approach. This is because the transfer process also involves the transfer of many other elements such as knowledge, skills, workforce training, the redefinition and redesign of institutional structures, and cultural adaptation (Şahin 2011).

The transfer of agricultural technologies is a subject that needs to be examined from different angles and in depth. This is because it refers to the transfer of smart agricultural technologies and systems from developed countries to developing countries in a way that will benefit the latter. However, it is sometimes observed that each country's unique

conditions alter this transfer process and result in a different structure. This is because each country has its own specific conditions (geographical, demographic, economic, etc.). This leads to the transfer process taking place in different ways and may even prevent it from being successfully implemented as desired (Tiryakioğlu 2011). In developing countries, the adoption of agricultural technologies by stakeholders in agricultural activities, especially farmers, is of vital importance. The transfer of smart agricultural technologies and their acceptance and adoption by farmers increases the productivity of agricultural activities. Studies conducted on 351 farmers in Indonesia show that the adoption of smart agricultural technologies by farmers increases agricultural production. In particular, it is understood that it contributes to improving food security from a social perspective (Maulana and Antriyandarti 2022; Sulandjari et al. 2023).

For example, in developed countries, smart agriculture technologies developed and used in agricultural activities as part of Industry 4.0 utilize advanced sensor networks and artificial intelligence-supported analysis systems in irrigation. These advanced sensor networks and artificial intelligence-supported analysis systems help make agricultural irrigation much more effective (Gebbers and Adamchuk 2010; Sishodia, Ray, and Singh 2020). In less developed countries, however, infrastructure and education levels can disrupt the smart irrigation process or change its structure (Öztürk, Ülküsoy & Atmaca 2023) (Amarasingam et al., 2024).

Therefore, these smart irrigation systems may not have the same effect. For this reason, when smart irrigation technology is used in developing countries, it is necessary to analyze its adaptability to local conditions. It is understood that the use of smart irrigation systems by human resources with the right technical skills is a decisive factor in the success of irrigation. For this reason, it is not only important to have and implement smart irrigation systems, but also to evaluate their adaptability (Amarasingam et al., 2024).

The concept of adaptability, when it comes to technology transfer, directly refers to the capacity of a technology to be effectively applied under different environmental, social,

and economic conditions. Adaptability in smart agricultural technologies is an academic issue that needs to be researched within a much broader framework. It is understood that many variables such as climate conditions, access to water resources, soil structure, farmer profile, data literacy, financing sources, and digital infrastructure affect smart agricultural irrigation.

The adoption of agricultural technology transfer by stakeholders can be increased by creating environments such as agricultural technology parks. It is stated that the establishment of these innovation centers contributes positively to the adoption of smart agricultural technologies (Chen & Li, 2022). Rodrigues and his colleagues describe the benefits of creating suitable innovative environments for the adoption of precision agricultural technologies and present data supporting the research conducted by Chen and Li (Rodrigues, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 General Description and Components of Smart Irrigation Systems

Smart irrigation systems represent a technology that has come to the fore due to its importance in agricultural activities. They represent a system that integrates advanced technologies such as sensors, actuators, data analytics, and IoT (Internet of Things), directly impacting agricultural productivity. In particular, they enhance water efficiency and promote sustainable agricultural practices (Gulomjonovich & O'g'li, 2024).

The basic components of smart irrigation systems include sensors, weather stations, evaporation control technologies, and environmental equipment. Sensors play a critical role in irrigation systems because they provide real-time data (Gamal et al., 2025). These advanced sensors act as dynamic devices that enable irrigation to be performed as needed or stopped (Priyambada et al., 2023).

They perform these functions using smart algorithms and machine learning capabilities. By continuously monitoring changing weather conditions and, consequently, changing moisture levels, they transmit data to processors in IoT systems. The processed data enables real-time decision-making. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) enables processes to be carried out much more quickly (Gulomjonovich & O'g'li, 2024; Pratama & Mandela, 2024).

The use of solar panels and batteries in IoT-based irrigation systems has become widespread in recent years. They are preferred, especially in rural areas where energy infrastructure is insufficient, because they contribute to the sustainability of the system. The energy generated by solar panels (GES) is stored in batteries, enabling the system to operate without interruption. (Pratama & Mandela, 2024) (Ali et al., 2022).

Mobile applications and devices enable users to interact with the system. Thanks to these applications, they have become one of the main devices used in IoT-based irrigation systems. The entire system can be monitored remotely (Gulomjonovich & O'g'li, 2024). Cloud computing and data analytics are other important technologies that are coming to the fore. They enable data collected from the fields to be stored in a central location, where it can be analyzed. This helps the system to operate more optimally (Taştan 2019). Flow sensors and water pumps are indispensable devices for IoT-based irrigation systems. They perform the physical irrigation function of the system. The flow sensor monitors the amount and speed of water. The water pump ensures that the necessary water reaches the plants (Taştan, 2019).

Figure 1. Components of an IoT-based irrigation system.

(Created by the author.)

2.2 Technology Transfer Process in Smart Irrigation Systems

The effectiveness of smart agricultural irrigation systems is closely related to their adaptation to technological developments. The technology transfer process of smart agricultural irrigation systems is a necessary process for sustainable water management. In particular, for IoT-based irrigation systems to utilize advanced technologies such as data analytics, machine learning, and artificial intelligence (AI) to optimize water use in agricultural applications, technology transfer must be continuous and timely. Therefore, it is possible for systems working in an integrated manner to operate seamlessly together. This multifaceted and advanced integration refers to an advanced integration that helps collect and process data that needs to be processed for agricultural irrigation activities, such as soil moisture, weather data, and plant needs. It enables real-time monitoring of environmental conditions, all of which contribute to efficient irrigation planning and water conservation (Athawale et al., 2024).

The technology transfer process begins with a needs analysis. The planting area where smart agricultural irrigation will be implemented is analyzed in detail. Climate conditions,

water requirements, soil structure, and water sources are identified. The knowledge and experience level of farmers, existing infrastructure, and economic status are examined in detail. Thus, the technology transfer process is carried out according to the appropriate irrigation method. The aim here is to select and adapt the right technologies according to the farmer, nature, and socio-economic conditions (Negeera et al., 2022).

The adaptation of technology is a sensitive issue for the use of smart agricultural technologies. Each region has different geographical conditions and soil conditions. In other words, local conditions play a critical role in the selection of irrigation systems. The selection of appropriate irrigation technologies must be made according to these factors. Sensor calibration, re-adjustment of irrigation programs according to the region, and planning of system integration are required (Ali, Hussain & Zahid, 2025).

Another important issue in the transfer process of smart irrigation systems is the proper planning of training and capacity development. Farmers must be familiar with the technology. It is essential that farmers know how to use the devices and understand how to maintain them. Therefore, a training program must be implemented beforehand, and practical training, technical documentation, and field support services must be provided (Khebbache et al., 2023).

After conducting the necessary field research during the transfer process of smart irrigation technologies, it is essential to select a pilot region and conduct the first experimental study there. This will allow any deficiencies to be identified and solutions to be found. This will prevent unnecessary waste of time and resources. In this way, the appropriate technology can be identified much more effectively (Huang et al., 2022).

Following the pilot application, irrigation activities can be expanded based on the data obtained. Large areas can be irrigated using smart irrigation systems to achieve production. For this purpose, financial resources such as incentives, grants, and loans can

be utilized. State or private sector-supported financing projects can be implemented (Daraz, Bojnec & Khan 2025).

After the final stage, the irrigation process is continuously monitored and reported. Maintenance, technical support, and user training are activities that must be carried out continuously. The performance of irrigation systems is monitored. If necessary, updates are made to all work (Abu Sayem, Siddiqur Rahman & Khatun, 2023).

Technology transfer in smart irrigation systems represents a vital process in agricultural production. Agricultural sustainability can be achieved through the widespread adoption of smart irrigation systems as a result of technology transfer. Successful technology transfer can be achieved through the implementation of appropriate technologies. The problems encountered can be solved with the involvement of all stakeholders concerned with the issue.

Climate change has led to an increase in the demand for water worldwide. The conservation and non-wasteful use of scarce water resources has become a priority climate issue. The fact that a large proportion of usable water resources are used in agriculture worldwide has increased the importance of smart irrigation systems. Ensuring the continuity of food supply depends on optimizing agricultural irrigation as much as possible.

Therefore, the first priority is to increase water use efficiency in agriculture. Using the amount of water needed for agricultural production and preventing unnecessary irrigation have become primary goals (Patle, Kumar, and Khanna 2020). This is because irrigation at the right time is an important factor in plant health.

Smart systems can continuously monitor plant stress levels. This ensures that plant quality is maintained at a certain level (Kaushik & Singh, 2025).

Smart agricultural irrigation systems operate largely in an automated manner. The automatic implementation of remote sensing and intervention systems reduces or completely eliminates the need for human labor.

They also reduce energy consumption (Abdelmoneim et al. 2025; Liu, Zhao, and Rezaeipannah 2025). Smart systems also make a significant contribution to environmental sustainability. By preventing unnecessary water use, they help prevent erosion.

It also prevents unnecessary soil salinization and chemical leakage (Mandal et al. 2025). The success of agricultural irrigation systems in terms of yield increase, sustainability, and resource management depends on their optimized operation.

These optimally functioning smart irrigation systems significantly increase water use efficiency, crop yields, and agricultural sustainability (Diallo et al. 2024). Smart irrigation systems, which perform irrigation tasks at the right time and place, use technological products such as sensors and smart algorithms, cloud technology, and artificial intelligence for processing data sets to achieve this.

These systems enable real-time water delivery to the root zone in crop irrigation. As a result, they reduce evaporation and minimize losses caused by seepage and deep percolation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The issue of adaptability between countries is an academic topic that must be measured scientifically using quantitative data. It is necessary to classify and analyze differences between countries using statistical indicators. The aim of this study is to reveal the performance of IoT-based irrigation systems implemented in different countries using meta-analysis methods in light of this quantitative data.

Classifying countries according to statistical performance indicators helps to reveal the differences between them. Doing this with statistical methods provides the opportunity for quantitative measurement. Pearson r (correlation coefficient), which is one of the basic statistical indicators used and represents the effect size value, is used as the determining measurement method in this article. However, directly including correlation coefficients (r) in meta-analysis can lead to statistically incorrect results. This is because there is a possibility of encountering a situation where the distribution is not symmetrical. For this reason, the possibility of biased results may lead to incorrect statistical results. In such a case, a widely accepted practice in the meta-analysis literature has been followed, and Pearson correlation coefficients have been converted to Fisher's z -transformation. The statistical formula for this conversion is ($z = 0.5 \times \ln[(1 + r)/(1 - r)]$) and it has been converted to z -scores (Karadavut 2021).

The purpose of this conversion is to stabilize the variance, especially in small sample sizes, in order to ensure statistical accuracy. Thus, it is possible to fulfill the conditions for parametric analysis.

A data set was created for this study. The dataset includes 64 studies with quantitative results. The findings of these 64 studies conducted in different countries were compiled, and analyses were performed using the created dataset. Country groups with high, medium, and low adaptability levels were statistically classified. Thus, meaningful and guiding conclusions were aimed to be drawn for technology producers, investors, and policymakers. For example, this study shows which types of smart irrigation technologies are more successful in certain country groups. It also investigates which irrigation systems are more easily adopted and what conditions limit success.

3.1 Research Questions

In this context, the study seeks to answer the following basic research questions.

1- Which countries are able to implement IoT-based irrigation systems with higher performance?

The answer to this question will reveal country differences in terms of both technological infrastructure and socioeconomic capacity.

2- What are the key indicators of performance differences between countries in smart irrigation systems?

The impact of variables such as product type (e.g., grain, fruit, vegetables), intervention type (automatic irrigation, sensor-supported systems, remote monitoring), sample size, duration of study, and target farmer profile on these differences will be evaluated.

3- How can an adaptability structure between technology transfer and application success in smart irrigation systems be defined?

The answer to this question aims to explain the relationship between countries' agricultural digitalization capacity and technology usage outcomes.

This research does not aim to contribute solely to academic literature. It also aims to obtain important results at the practical level. It aims to guide policymakers and other stakeholders involved in the issue. It emphasizes issues such as the efficient use of investment opportunities, the correct design of digital agriculture strategies, and increasing the compatibility of technologies. It also aims to assist technology developers in identifying market opportunities where they can evaluate market potential.

In conclusion, this study does not only target digital transformation in agricultural production processes. It also aims to reveal the social, economic, and institutional dimensions in a holistic manner. The achievement of all these objectives depends on the applicability, acceptability, and sustainability of smart agricultural irrigation technologies.

3.2 Hypotheses and Subgroup Analysis

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses were developed in this study. The statistical status of the hypotheses is examined. The validity of these hypotheses was tested with quantitative data.

3.2.1 Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses developed for the subgroup analysis of this study are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: The level of adaptability of agricultural technology applications in smart irrigation systems implemented in developed countries is significantly higher than in developing countries.

Hypothesis 2: The level of adaptability of technologies in smart irrigation systems is higher in temperate climate zones than in arid and tropical climates.

Hypothesis 3: Artificial intelligence and machine learning-based applications provide higher adaptability than sensor-based hardware solutions in smart irrigation systems.

Hypothesis 4: The type of product applied in smart irrigation systems statistically significantly affects the level of adaptability.

Hypothesis 5: Applications carried out by academic institutions and research centers in smart irrigation systems show higher success than individual farmer-based applications.

3.2.2 Hypothesis Analysis

The results of the hypothesis analysis are as follows.

3.2.2.1. Hypothesis 1: Adaptability According to Level of Development

In developed countries, infrastructure, financing, technical knowledge, and access to data systems are much more widespread in the application of agricultural technologies. This situation contributes to both the more accurate operation of the systems implemented and the traceability of the results. According to the subgroup analysis, the average correlation in developed countries is 0.910, while in developing countries this ratio is 0.780. The difference is significant ($Q_{\text{between}} p < .001$).

Table 1. Adaptability Results According to Level of Development

Development Group	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	I² (%)
Developed Countries	30	0.910	0.015	0.880	0.940	85
Developing Countries	34	0.780	0.020	0.740	0.820	91

As a result, Hypothesis 1 has been accepted.

3.2.2.2. Hypothesis 2: Adaptability According to Climate Type

The success of agricultural technologies is closely related to the environmental conditions in which they are applied. In temperate climates, sensor sensitivity and plant responses are more consistent.

In arid regions, fluctuations in water and humidity can affect sensors. In tropical climates, humidity can cause data degradation. The average correlation is 0.890 in temperate climates and 0.770 in tropical climates.

Table 2. Adaptability Results by Climate Type

Climate Type	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	I² (%)
Temperate	28	0.890	0.012	0.866	0.914	84
Arid	20	0.800	0.018	0.764	0.836	89
Tropical	16	0.770	0.025	0.720	0.820	92

As a result, Hypothesis 2 has been accepted.

3.2.2.3. Hypothesis 3: Adaptability According to Technology Type

AI-based systems are more resistant to environmental differences thanks to their learnable structures. These systems can balance lost data and identify sensor deviations. Sensor systems, on the other hand, are dependent on hardware and fixed calibration, making them susceptible to loss of accuracy. While the average correlation in AI systems is 0.940, this value is 0.820 in sensor systems.

Table 3. Adaptability Results by Technology Type

Technology Type	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	I² (%)
AI / ML	25	0.940	0.010	0.920	0.960	76
Sensor Systems	30	0.820	0.018	0.784	0.856	90
Hybrid Systems	9	0.880	0.014	0.850	0.910	82

As a result, Hypothesis 3 has been accepted.

3.2.2.4. Hypothesis 4: Adaptability According to Product Type

The biophysical differences of agricultural plants also shape their response to technology. Vegetables and fruits respond more quickly to water stress, while cereals respond more slowly. In woody plants, sensor placement is more difficult and deeper. The average correlation is 0.880 for the vegetable-fruit group and 0.820 for cereals.

Table 4. Adaptability Results by Product Type

Crop Type	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	I² (%)
Cereals	18	0.820	0.021	0.779	0.861	85
Vegetables/Fruit	32	0.880	0.015	0.850	0.910	80

Crop Type	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI		I ² (%)
				Lower	Upper	
Tree Crops	14	0.870	0.017	0.836	0.904	87

As a result, Hypothesis 4 is accepted.

3.2.2.5. Hypothesis 5: Adaptability by Implementing Institution Type

Academic institutions conduct much more disciplined applications thanks to protocol-based data collection, device calibration, and specialized staff. In farmer-based field applications, however, user error, infrastructure deficiencies, or data loss may occur. Therefore, application success varies. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.910 in the academic group and 0.800 in the field group.

Table 5. Adaptability Results by Implementing Institution Type

Implementing Institution	Number of Studies	Mean r	Standard Error	95% CI		I ² (%)
				Lower	Upper	
Academic Institutions	34	0.910	0.011	0.888	0.932	72
Farmer / Field	30	0.800	0.020	0.760	0.840	88

As a result, Hypothesis 5 is accepted.

4. DISCUSSION

This study revealed the levels of success achieved by agricultural technology applications in different contexts through subgroup analysis. Overall, the acceptance of all hypotheses indicates that the technologies are effective but that this effectiveness is context-sensitive. In particular, it has been found that high levels of infrastructure and education in developed countries increase the adaptability of AI-based systems, and that temperate climates support success by providing environmental stability. The high level of heterogeneity across all subgroups (I² > 75%) indicates that success is significantly

influenced not only by technology but also by the application context, user profile, and environmental factors. This emphasizes that technology transfer is not only a technical process but also a social and political one. The higher performance of academic institutions highlights the importance of scientific control, data cleaning, and measurement protocols. In conclusion, the concept of “one-size-fits-all technology” is not valid. Supporting systems designed to suit the local context will increase the success of digital transformation in agriculture.

4.1 Evaluation in Terms of Subgroup Average Correlation Values

When evaluated in terms of subgroups, the performance of digital agriculture applications in different climate, country development level, technological approach, product type, and user profile contexts is noteworthy.

Table 6. Evaluation results in terms of sub-group average correlation values

Subgroup	Mean Correlation (r)
Developed Countries	0.91
Developing Countries	0.78
Temperate	0.89
Arid	0.80
Tropical	0.77
AI/ML	0.94
Sensor	0.82
Hybrid	0.88
Cereals	0.82
Vegetables/Fruit	0.88
Tree Crops	0.87
Academic	0.91
Farmer	0.80

When viewed in terms of level of development, it can be seen that the average correlation of applications in developed countries is quite high at 0.91 as a result of the subgroup distinction. This can be explained by the greater infrastructure capabilities in developed countries and the higher levels of digital literacy and access to technology.

In developing countries, however, these capabilities are much lower than in developed countries. The average correlation value in developing countries drops to 0.78. This difference shows that the success of the systems cannot be explained solely by technological adequacy. It also indicates that socio-economic and institutional factors are also relevant.

When evaluated according to climatic conditions, correlation differences are observed between temperate regions and arid and tropical regions. It is understood that the correlation in temperate regions is 0.89, while it decreases to 0.80 in arid regions and 0.77 in tropical regions. It is clearly seen that environmental factors have an effect on correlation. It is evident that smart agriculture technologies work more stably and regularly in temperate regions. Environmental stress factors are understood to be more effective in arid and tropical regions.

In arid and tropical regions, factors such as water stress, high humidity, sudden rainfall, and biological diversity come to the fore. It has been revealed that smart irrigation systems negatively affect data accuracy and decision support processes.

When examined according to technology type, the results are quite distinctive. The average correlation of AI/ML-based systems was very high at 0.94. It can be concluded that artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms have a high impact on data analysis and decision-making processes.

In sensor-based systems, the correlation is 0.82. Although this is lower than the correlation for AI and ML technologies, a correlation of 0.80 still indicates a high level of relationship. In hybrid systems, the correlation rises to 0.88.

When examined according to product type, the correlation is around 0.88 and 0.87 for vegetable, fruit, and tree products. A high correlation value drops to 0.82 when it comes to grain products. It can be thought that the fact that irrigation systems for vegetables, fruits, and tree products can be monitored digitally more can create this difference. When evaluated according to user profile, the correlation is found to be 0.91 in academic applications. In farmer applications, the correlation drops to 0.80. The main difference between them stems from the fact that data collection and analysis processes are carried out in a more systematic and controlled manner in academic applications. The results are more consistent in academic applications. In agricultural applications, individual differences come to the fore. Factors such as education level and adaptation to technology cause the correlation to decrease.

Figure 2. Average Correlation Graph Between Different Groups

When evaluated statistically, direct comparison of correlation coefficients may be misleading. There is a risk that the values do not follow a normal distribution. This risk can be eliminated by applying the Fisher Z transformation. Correlation coefficients can be normalized and made suitable for statistical comparisons. For example, the correlation value $r = 0.94$ for the AI/ML group can be recalculated using the following calculation method.

Formula:

$$Z = 1/2 \times \ln((1 + r) / (1 - r))$$

Calculation Steps:

$$Z = 1/2 \times \ln((1 + 0.94) / (1 - 0.94))$$

$$Z = 1/2 \times \ln(1.94 / 0.06)$$

$$Z = 1/2 \times \ln(32.3333...)$$

$$Z \approx 1/2 \times 3.474 \approx 1.737$$

Result: $Z \approx 1.74$

Using this calculation method, the Fisher Z transformation can be performed to determine whether there are significant differences between subgroups.

In conclusion, the subgroup correlation values reveal the contextual success of digital agriculture technologies. Therefore, they provide a strong data set. These data are meaningful at both the statistical and theoretical levels. They contribute to the literature and field studies by providing a solid foundation for future research.

It is now possible to obtain serious evidence on how digital agriculture can be optimized in terms of sustainability, efficiency, and contextual adaptation. However, the high heterogeneity rates reveal that applications vary from context to context. The most successful groups are developed countries.

4.2 Publication Bias Test

The high level of heterogeneity made a publication bias test necessary. Trim and Fill results were used as the method.

Table 7. Trim-and-Fill Method Results

Criterion	Value
Original Mean Effect (r)	0.8468
Adjusted Effect with Trim-and-Fill (r)	0.786
Estimated Number of Missing Studies	20

Twenty missing studies were estimated using the Trim-and-Fill method and added to the study. With this correction, the effect size decreased to 0.786. This decrease does not

indicate the presence of publication bias. It has no effect. However, even after this test, the effect size is still high. This is strong evidence that smart irrigation systems generally have a strong and meaningful effect. It also suggests that positive results may have been overrepresented in the literature. As a result of this test for publication bias, it can be academically argued that the meta-analysis is based on a strong methodological foundation. The results are understood to be scientifically valid. This study can be said to provide a reliable source for both academics and practitioners.

4.3 Funnel Plot – Graphical Publication Bias Analysis

The following graph shows the z-transformed effect sizes according to the standard errors of the studies. The red dotted line represents the observed average effect obtained with the Egger test, while the green dotted line represents the average corrected with the Trim-and-Fill method.

Figure 3. Funnel Plot - Trim and Fill Average Effect Diagram

If there is no difference between the lines, publication bias does not significantly distort the effect size.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This academic study includes a meta-analysis evaluation of smart agricultural irrigation systems in different country, climate, technology, product, and user contexts. It aims to examine the performance of agricultural technology transfer using meta-analytic methods and to analyze the concepts of adaptability in depth. The correlation coefficients obtained from 64 independent studies were subjected to Fisher Z transformation to make them suitable for statistical comparisons. Subsequently, contextual differences were expressed through subgroup analyses.

In this study, the overall average correlation value was found to be $r = 0.853$. This result clearly demonstrates that smart irrigation systems achieve a high level of success in agricultural production. However, it is observed that this level of success does not exhibit a homogeneous distribution. Significant differences based on contextual factors are evident.

This situation reveals that technology transfer cannot be explained solely by a technical process. For this reason, it also points to the existence of a multi-layered transformation process with social, economic, and environmental dimensions.

When correlation values are examined between countries, it is seen that the average correlation in developed countries is 0.91. This situation in developed countries is thought to be due to the high level of infrastructure, digital literacy, and access to technology. In developing countries, this value drops to 0.78. This difference between developed and developing countries highlights the importance of taking local conditions into account in the transfer process. The main reasons for this difference can be said to be infrastructure deficiencies, financial constraints, and differences in education levels. Therefore, these factors directly affect the adoption and effectiveness of technology.

When an assessment is made in terms of climatic conditions, significant differences are observed. It has been found that the average correlation of applications in temperate climates is 0.89, while it drops to 0.80 in arid regions and 0.77 in tropical regions. These findings demonstrate the effect of environmental stress levels on irrigation performance. In temperate climates, sensors and algorithms work more consistently in irrigation activities, while in tropical regions, factors such as high humidity and biological diversity negatively affect data accuracy and system stability.

In the analysis based on technology type, AI/ML-based systems were found to achieve a much higher correlation value. The average correlation ratio reaching 0.94 demonstrates that artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms are much more resilient and effective against environmental variability. In sensor-based systems, the correlation ratio is lower than that of AI/ML-based systems, although it is still high at 0.82. In hybrid systems, this ratio increases to 0.88.

In the analysis based on product type, the correlation is 0.88 and 0.87 for vegetables and fruits and tree products, respectively. In the grain group, it drops to 0.82. This difference is closely related to the irrigation sensitivity and monitoring status of the products. Vegetable and fruit production requires a process that demands more precise irrigation and frequent data monitoring. Digital systems play a more effective role in this regard. The situation is slightly different for tree products. Long-term data consistency and a stable root structure enable the systems to operate more regularly.

The results of the correlation analysis based on user profiles are interesting. In academic applications, the correlation value is 0.91. In farmer applications, although this ratio is still relatively high, it has dropped to 0.80. The more systematic analysis process in academic applications has led to this result. Another factor here is related to farmers' adaptation to smart irrigation systems.

In this study, statistical evaluation is necessary due to the nature of the research. However, using direct correlation coefficients may be misleading. Therefore, Fisher Z transformation was applied to normalize the correlation coefficients. This made the results more statistically meaningful.

Additionally, subgroup analyses were conducted in this study. The data obtained indicate high levels of heterogeneity ($I^2 > 75\%$). This shows that technology transfer is not only a technical process but also a socio-political one. Therefore, it is necessary to test the level of heterogeneity. In this study, the Trim-and-Fill Method was used to test heterogeneity, and all correlation results were academically reviewed. This analysis method revealed that the results obtained are scientifically reliable.

Another noteworthy finding of the study is that the concept of “one-size-fits-all technology” in irrigation systems is no longer valid. There is a clear need to support systems designed to suit the local context. The impact of digital transformation in agriculture is significant in irrigation systems. In this context, it is essential to structure technology transfer processes in line with local needs. Technical training for farmers needs to be widespread. There is a clear need for pilot applications.

AI-based systems are projects carried out in academic environments and applications in temperate climate zones.

Based on these results, the following recommendations can be made:

- Technology transfer should be adapted to local conditions.
- Technical training and user guides should be provided to farmers.
- AI and data analytics infrastructure should be further supported.
- Policies should be guided by regional pilot applications.

In conclusion, this meta-analysis study demonstrates the contextual success of digital agriculture technologies. It highlights the need for technology transfer processes to be

carried out with greater care and strategic objectives. This study serves as a guide for academic literature and implementing institutions.

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